

Data Management Plan I

Action Acronym: PEACE

Action title: Project 101101343 - Pressurized Efficient Alkaline Electrolyser

Author: Grant Garant

Contributing authors: All project partners

Date: January 23, 2024

The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members.

Co-funded by
the European Union

PEACE Consortium

Beneficiary name	Short name
Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (DE)	DLR
Materials Mates Italia SRL (IT)	MMI
Technische Universiteit Eindhoven (NL)	TU/e
Brandenburgische Technische Universität Cottbus Senftenberg (DE)	BTU CS
Grant Garant sro (CZ)	GG
HyCC B.V. (NL)	HYCC
Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DK)	DTU

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AEL	Alkaline electrolysis
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence
CC-BY-SA	Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike Licence
CC0	Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication
DMP	Data Management Plan
EB	Executive Board
FMEA	Failure Mode and Effects Analysis
HAZOP	Hazard and Operability Analysis
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
M	Month
PEDR	Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results
PM	Person-month
WP	Working package

Table of contents

1. Executive Summary.....	3
2. PEACE Project Summary	4
3. PEACE Data Summary.....	5
3.1. DMP objectives.....	5
3.2. Data management in the PEACE project.....	5
3.3. Summary of PEACE data and other research outputs.....	5
4. PEACE FAIR data (Findable-Accessible-Interoperable-Reuseable)	10
5. Conclusion	13
6. References.....	14

1. Executive Summary

PEACE is a research and innovation action project financed by the [Clean Hydrogen Partnership](#) under the Horizon Europe. The PEACE project is coordinated by Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. ([DLR](#)). Its main objective is to reduce the levelized cost of hydrogen via development of an innovative high-pressure alkaline electrolysis technology for hydrogen production.

This PEACE Data management Plan (DMP) is based on a PEACE deliverable of the same name which was delivered to the granting authority in M3 (August 2023) with a sensitive dissemination level. The current version represents a public version of the deliverable and is produced for public use.

The PEACE DMP is guided by the EU Open Science policy. Firstly, it aims to identify the main datasets and other research outputs that will be produced within the project. Secondly, it ensures that the project's data management follows the FAIR principles of data policy. Thirdly, it represents a living platform for the project, allowing for further data management updates and enhancements. The DMP has been prepared by PEACE member GG based on an internal survey of PEACE participants during months (M) 1-2 of the project implementation.

The PEACE consortium has identified seven datasets and thirteen other research outputs (mostly public deliverables) that will be produced in the project. All research data and outputs will be managed responsibly in accordance with the FAIR principles. Findability will be ensured through the use of persistent identifiers, metadata frameworks, and keywords. All datasets and outputs will be stored in trusted repositories, and open access will be provided whenever possible. However, some datasets have been identified as sensitive, and open access is currently considered contrary to the beneficiary's legitimate interests (as commercial exploitation is foreseen).

PEACE datasets available through open access will be licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike (CC-BY-SA), and metadata will be licensed under Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0). PEACE plans to use the Zenodo repository for making datasets publicly and permanently available.

Interoperability and re-use of PEACE data will be enhanced by using open data formats, keywords, metadata, or readme files. The preservation of PEACE datasets is guaranteed for at least 5 years after the end of the project.

The PEACE DMP was delivered to the granting authority in M3 (August 2023) of the project implementation period. It will be continuously updated as needed, with new versions issued in M18 and M36 of the project implementation.

2. PEACE Project Summary

The PEACE project is funded by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership under the Horizon Europe programme and is coordinated by Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (DLR). PEACE represents a challenging research and innovation action in the field of hydrogen production, using the alkaline electrolysis (AEL) technologies. AEL technologies are known for their low investment costs and excellent scalability. The PEACE project aims to further improve the levelized cost of hydrogen produced by AEL. Therefore, efforts are focused on enhancing efficiency, maximizing current densities, and enabling better integration with downstream processes. By carefully designing a high-pressure stack and system, the performance and overall efficiency of the AEL process will be significantly improved, eliminating the need for additional compression for downstream processes. This, in turn, reduces the capital and operational expenses associated with hydrogen compressors, which are a substantial part of electrolysis systems' cost.

Within the PEACE project, under the coordination of DLR, a demonstrator of an AEL system exceeding 50 kW, capable of operating at pressures more than 50 bar, will be designed and developed. This is achieved through a novel concept involving two-stage pressurization. The integration of advanced components, innovative design, and optimized operation strategies will be explored through modelling and experimental testing, ultimately aiming to demonstrate a system with impressive efficiency characteristics. The successful implementation of this technology promises a significant reduction in the cost of green hydrogen production.

The PEACE project scientific objectives are reinforced by a strong focus on sustainability and circularity aspects, as well as dedicated outreach activities. The consortium comprises four research and development centres (DLR, TU/e, BTU CS, DTU) with established expertise in alkaline stack, system, and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), one of the largest hydrogen production and utilization companies globally (HYCC) and two SMEs (MMI, GG). This collaboration ensures a comprehensive approach to achieving the project's goals.

Finally, the project aims to propose use cases and the concept of an integrated plant. By combining all these developments, the goal is to achieve a technological breakthrough with a clear commercial perspective, positioning Europe as a leader in highly pressurized AEL technology within the next three years. For more information visit our website: <https://www.h2peace.eu/>

3. PEACE Data Summary

3.1. DMP objectives

PEACE is a research and innovation action project funded by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership under Horizon Europe programme. Over the course of its 36-month implementation, several digital research datasets from different PEACE consortium members will be generated. The formulation of a viable data management plan to guide the project consortium through the processes of data storage, availability, accessibility, and re-use is essential. Furthermore, the guiding principles of the EU Open Science policy (broadly outlined in Annex V of the EU grants Annotated Grant Agreement) provide a pathway for creating a comprehensive yet user-friendly plan to effectively manage data within the PEACE project. This plan aids the consortium in achieving efficient implementation of research objectives and additionally, facilitates effective communication and dissemination of project results.

The PEACE DMP is produced within the Working package (WP) 1 task 1.5. Its main objectives are to:

- Identify main datasets that will be produced
- Ensure data management in line with FAIR principles
- Provide a living platform for data management updates and enhancements

The PEACE DMP covers digital research data generated within the project as well as other research outputs (namely public deliverables). It is based on dataset information that has been collected through an internal survey of the project consortium within M1-M2 of the project. This document represents the initial version of the DMP, developed at an early stage of project implementation. It should be regarded as a dynamic document that will be continuously updated and expanded as necessary, with regular updates planned for M18 and M36.

3.2. Data management in the PEACE project

Data management represents one of the tasks of the WP1, overseen by the GG. GG prepares the DMP in close cooperation and discussion with all PEACE members, aiming to achieve the established DMP objectives. Additionally, GG guides all the consortium through the data life cycle process and informs them about their relevant data management obligations. GG is responsible for periodical reviews of the DMP, in collaboration with all PEACE members.

At the institutional level, the Executive Board (EB) members, who represent each participating entity, are responsible for addressing data management issues. The EB members serve as the primary points of contact for GG regarding data-related matters.

3.3. Summary of PEACE data and other research outputs

PEACE project is structured to six work packages – four are dedicated to research and innovation in the field of hydrogen production with AEL technology. The remaining WP1

focuses on project management and WP6 on communication, dissemination and exploitation issues. The consortium has identified seven broad datasets that will be used in the PEACE project. Their brief description can be found in Figure 1. Moreover, thirteen other research outputs will be produced (see Figure 2) – mostly project deliverables that are destined for public use¹.

Datasets

Fig 1. PEACE datasets

Dataset No.	Dat_1	Dat_2	Dat_3	Dat_4	Dat_5	Dat_6	Dat_7
Name	Cell component development, scaling up and qualification	Operation strategies and simulation	Cell components development and qualification	Dual-stage high-pressure alkaline electrolyser operation	Integration concept of HP-AEL in a chemical plant	Conventional H2 production via AEL	PEACE H2 production
Owner	DLR	DLR	TU/e	BTU CS	HYCC BV	DTU	DTU
WP/task	2/2.1	5/5.1-5.5	2/2.1-2.3	4/4.1-4.7	5/5.6	6/6.1	6/6.1
Description	Electrochemical testing of cells and short stack	TEMPEST simulation data on the stack behaviour in a system in transient conditions.	Qualification of cell components	Experimental data from the demonstrator in operation	Process design data including sketches, mass & energy balances, cost estimates	The life cycle inventory of materials and energy necessary to produce H2 conventionally via electrolysis (benchmark for the PEACE data)	The life cycle inventory of materials and energy necessary to produce hydrogen via PEACE AEL
Type of data	Numeric, text, images	Numeric, text, images	Numeric	Numeric, text, images	Numeric, images, dtbs, models	Dtbs, models	Dtbs, models
Data format	Doc/docx, pdf, xls/xlsx, txt, jpg, tiff, png	Doc/docx, pdf, xls/xlsx, txt, jpg, tiff, mat-file	Xls/xlsx, sql, ids/idf	Xls/xlsx, pdf, csv, txt, jpg, png	Doc/docx, pdf, xls/xlsx, jpg, tiff	Xls/xlsx, pdf, txt	Xls/xlsx, pdf, txt
Repository	Yes - Zenodo	Yes - Zenodo	YES - 4TU.Researchdata	Yes - Open Energy Platform	Yes - Zenodo	YES - supplement material of an OA article + DTU repository	YES - supplement material of an OA article + DTU repository
Open access	Partly	Partly	Yes	Yes	Partly	Yes	Yes
Reasons for closed data	Commercial exploitation	Commercial exploitation	NA	NA	Commercial exploitation + sensitive info on beneficiary	NA	NA
Metadata	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

¹ Deliverables which dissemination level is "sensitive" will not be part of this DMP. First, they are not meant for public use and second, they are based on datasets already described in Figure 1.

PEACE datasets consist mainly of project-generated numerical data produced through direct measurements and simulations, except for the Life Cycle Inventory dataset (Dat_6). This benchmark dataset for the purpose of LCA of the PEACE high-pressure AEL will be based on re-used data collected from literature, surveys, or simulations. For LCA purposes, this dataset will be analysed jointly with dataset Dat_7, which covers similar characteristics generated from PEACE experiments and simulations. These datasets could prove valuable to LCA practitioners in fields such as renewable energy, energy production, hydrogen production, or power-to-X technologies.

Direct measurement data represent the core of the dataset Dat_1 and Dat_3, both at the level of the electrolytical cell and short stack, and Dat_4 at the PEACE demonstrator stack level. Datasets Dat_1 and Dat_3 will aid identifying optimal cell and stack components to achieve the defined system efficiency targets. They can be further used by researchers validating models and businesses involved in electrolysis hydrogen production. BTU CS data (Dat_4) constitutes outcome experimental data from the PEACE high-pressure AEL demonstrator, confirming its performance and efficiency. These data might further serve electrolysis companies, research entities, or production safety organisations.

Conversely, simulation data (Dat_2), collected by the coordinating institution DLR, will analyse the behaviour of the PEACE high-pressure AEL behaviour under transient conditions to formulate optimized operating strategies. These data might be a valuable resource for industries involved in electrolyser production, particularly water electrolysis and renewable energy, as well as for academics.

Lastly, HYCC B.V. will contribute with its dataset Dat_5, focusing on the integration of the PEACE high-pressure electrolyser within a chemical plant involving at least two downstream processes. This dataset encompasses numerical data, images, databases, and models. The design models will include heat integration, energy and mass balances, cost estimates, all with the aim to assessing and enhancing the impact of PEACE technologies. These data could prove highly valuable to companies and stakeholders interested in hydrogen production and/or use, as well as to researchers developing technologies who seek to assess impacts or establish design targets.

Most datasets are expected to have a **size** equal to or less than 5 GB. Simulation data (Dat_2) could be larger in size (in the tens of GBs), but a selection process will be employed to maintain a manageable size, keeping within the Zenodo repository's 50GB limit.

Other research outputs

Fig 2. Other research outputs - part A

	Oro_1	Oro_2	Oro_3	Oro_4	Oro_5	Oro_6	Oro_7
Name	Stack project specifications	Stack project calculation	Stack/cell operative drawings	PEACE DMP	D3.1 Stack components	D4.3 HAZOP/FMEA	D5.2 Optimized operation strategy
Owner	MMI	MMI	MMI	GG	MMI	MMI	DLR
WP/task	3/3.1-3.4	3/3.1-3.4	3/3.1-3.4	1/1.5	3/3.1-3.4	4/4.3	5/5.1-5.6
Description	List of the test items to	Calculation, description	Mechanical drawings of	Public version of	Public deliverable	Public deliverable	Public deliverable

	be produced, with features, materials and construction materials	and excel files of the sizing of different items	different produced items	the project DMP	on stack components (1 cell, end plates) qualified for pressure standing, mounting and initial testing	on HAZOP and FMEA analysis results and safety protocol	on optimized operation strategy for high pressure alkaline water electrolyser
Type of data	Text, images	Numeric, text, images, mechanical design	Numeric, text, images, mechanical design	Text	Numeric, images, dtbs, models	Numeric, text, images	Numeric, text, images
Data format	Xls/xlsx, doc/docx, pdf	Doc/docx, pdf, xls/xlsx	Doc/docx, pdf, 4D model	Pdf	Pdf, xls/xlsx, jpg, tiff	Pdf, xls/xlsx, jpg, tiff,	Pdf, xls/xlsx, jpg, tiff, png
Repository	Yes - Zenodo	Yes - Zenodo	Yes - Zenodo	Yes - Zenodo	Yes - Zenodo	Yes - Zenodo	Yes - Zenodo
Open access	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Reasons for closed data	x	X	Commercial exploitation	x	x	x	x
Metadata	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Fig 2. Other research outputs – part B

	Oro_8	Oro_9	Oro_10	Oro_11	Oro_12	Oro_13
Name	D6.2 Project website and PR	D6.3 Public workshop	D6.8 LCA	PEDR (public version)	D6.9 Update I of PEDR	D6.10 Update II of PEDR
Owner	GG	DLR	DTU	GG	GG	GG
WP/task	6/6.2	6/6.3	6/6.1	6/6.4	6/6.4	6/6.4
Description	Public deliverable on operational project website; communication and PR kit	Public deliverable on project workshop (report and presentations)	Public deliverable on the Life Cycle Analysis of the PEACE AEL	Public version of the project deliverable on the Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR)	Public deliverable on the first update of the PEDR	Public deliverable on the second update of the PEDR
Type of data	Text, images	Numeric, text, images	Numeric, text, images	Text, images	Text, images	Text, images
Data format	Pdf, jpg	Pdf, jpg	Pdf, jpg	Pdf, jpg	Pdf, jpg	Pdf, jpg
Repository	Yes - Zenodo	Yes - Zenodo	Yes - Zenodo	Yes - Zenodo	Yes - Zenodo	Yes - Zenodo
Open access	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Reasons for closed data	X	X	x	x	x	x
Metadata	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

At the outset of the PEACE project (M1-M2), the consortium anticipates producing approximately thirteen so called other research outputs. MMI will generate three outputs (Oro_1 – 3) related to the AEL stack, including stack specifications, calculations, and drawings. These outputs will be manufactured as part of the project and will be founded on datasets

from other PEACE members. These outputs are potentially useful for other electrolyser stack producers.

Among the thirty-one PEACE deliverables, eight have been assigned “public” dissemination level and will be covered within the PEACE data management plan. Oro_5 - Oro_7, along with Oro_9 (which summarises the achieved project results), represent scientific outputs that could prove valuable to researchers and businesses engaged in the hydrogen production. Deliverable Oro_10 aims to engage practitioners in matters of circularity and sustainability.

Conversely, Oro_8, and Oro_11 to Oro_13 represent communication and dissemination reports dedicated not only for the scientific community, but also for the general public. Ultimately, a public version of this DMP will be formulated and handled in accordance with the PEACE data plan and Open Science requirements.

4. PEACE FAIR data (Findable-Accessible-Interoperable-Reusable)

The PEACE project is built on open and collaborative work, and planned sharing of knowledge, whilst adhering to the data policy principle of achieving maximum openness as early and widely as possible. All research data generated by the PEACE project will be managed responsibly in accordance with the FAIR principles and Horizon Europe obligations (as described in the guidelines of the Annotated Grant Agreement - Article 17).

To ensure **findability** of PEACE data and other research outputs, all datasets (including other research outputs) will be assigned persistent identifier, preferably DOIs, through carefully selected trusted repositories. Metadata frameworks will accompany all datasets and will be openly accessible under the public domain dedication CC0. Metadata will provide information about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); Horizon Europe funding, grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata will include persistent identifiers for linked publications and other research outputs. Metadata will be stored within the repositories in JSON format and will be harvestable.

Simultaneously, PEACE datasets will employ common keywords such as hydrogen, alkaline electrolyser, and pressurization.

The **storage** of PEACE data will not be centralised, instead, the consortium will maintain the well-established storage practices of individual entities – ie., their respective institutional repositories. For internal sharing of data, other research outputs, or documents among the consortium, a project internal site (within the secure coordinator's server) will be used.

In line with the FAIR principles, PEACE datasets and other research outputs are intended to be deposited into **trusted repositories** as soon as possible and, at the latest, by the end of the project. If the given dataset underpins a scientific publication, it will be deposited no later than the time of publication. Most datasets and all other research outputs will use **Zenodo** repository (<https://zenodo.org/>), a trusted open-source repository with metadata openly available under CC0 licence, as mandated by Horizon Europe. Datasets on Zenodo will receive DOIs and can be linked to related publications or datasets. Availability of the data is planned at least for 10 years, but it will presumably align with the general conditions of the repository. PEACE members will not be obliged to include the information on software needed to read the data – this will remain an option only, though already agreed upon by some. Moreover, the creation of a PEACE project Zenodo community is being considered, which would bring together all PEACE Zenodo contributions in one location. There is also the option to join one of the established ZENODO communities (e.g., Open Energy Family).

DTU and TU/e will follow their usual practices and deposit their dataset (Dat_3, Dat_6, and Dat_7) within their respective trusted institutional repositories. DTU will use its university repository - **ScienceRepository** (<https://sciencerepository.dk/>) – which grants DOIs to all datasets and offers unlimited data storage. TU/e's repository, **4TU.Researchdata** (<https://data.4tu.nl>), is dedicated to science, engineering and design, offering up to 100GB of free data upload per year, with granted DOIs and openly published metadata, as required by Horizon Europe. BTU CS Dat_4 will be deposited in a domain-specific repository, the **Open**

Energy Platform (<https://openenergy-platform.org/>), an open infrastructure for energy system research. Datasets are identifiable (by id), openly accessible with rich metadata published.

PEACE data **accessibility** is presented in Figure 1 and 2. The consortium fully acknowledges Open Science and Open Access guidelines, thus ensuring that all PEACE data will be managed in line with the principle of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. For most datasets, open access will be granted at the time of datasets publication. However, open access to Dat_1, Dat_2, Dat_5, and Oro_3 is currently perceived as against the beneficiary’s legitimate interests (due to anticipated commercial exploitation). These sensitive datasets (as specified in Art. 13.1 of the PEACE Grant Agreement) are deemed commercially valuable, and their immediate openness would undermine their exploitation potential. As a result, they will remain closed (or under embargoed access) for the duration specified in the Data Sheet of the Grant Agreement (i.e., 5 years after the final payment). Nonetheless, PEACE beneficiaries support the EC Open Science policy and have outlined a potential division of these datasets. Part of the datasets Dat_1, Dat_2, and Dat_5 will remain closed for the reasons mentioned, while the other part will be accessible openly. However, the decision to keep certain PEACE data closed is subject to periodic review and may change.

The **interoperability** of PEACE data will be enhanced by employing open data formats (such as doc, pdf, xls, csv, jpg), or standard language keywords. As the FAIR data policy aims to optimise **the re-use of data**, the PEACE consortium will use well-described (meta)data to ensure the replicability of datasets across different contexts. For non-self-explanatory data, various strategies will be implemented to facilitate data validation and re-use. DTU will provide open comprehensive descriptions in the methodology section of the linked peer-reviewed articles that will be using Dat_6 and Dat_7. The cell components data of TU/e (Dat_3) will include additional relevant information, such as experimental conditions (temperature, pressure, concentration, type of electrode, reference electrode, type of potentiostat, etc.). Similarly, for the potentially open parts of the Dat_5, a readme file will be generated, containing all necessary information for interpretation and reproduction (reference conditions, modelling assumptions, settings, etc.).

Lastly, PEACE datasets in open access will be **licensed** under the latest available version of a Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike (CC-BY-SA), requiring attribution of authorship. Metadata will be licensed under Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0).

The **costs** associated with supporting the FAIR principles in PEACE will primarily involve datasets that directly underpin peer-reviewed articles (such as Dat_6, Dat_7), for which publication fees for open access are borne by the authors. Otherwise, the repositories that have been chosen by the PEACE members offer free data storage services. As personnel costs are assumed, a specific data steward position has not been established. However, data management falls within the responsibilities of GG, with approximately 0,75 PM dedicated to fulfilling this task. At the project institutional level, data management is the responsibility of each Executive Board member, and the related workload has not been calculated separately.

The **long-term preservation** of PEACE datasets is guaranteed for at least 5 years after the end of the project, in line with the general conditions of the chosen repositories, which typically offer data retention for more than 10 years.

Regarding **ethical or legal issues** affecting data sharing, it is important to note that no PEACE research datasets or other research outputs involve personal data. However, some PEACE members express concerns about the potential conflict between open data sharing and their intellectual property rights, given the anticipation of commercial exploitation. Therefore, certain datasets will not be fully accessible, as indicated in Figure 1.

Another potential source of data sensitivity has been introduced by BTU CS, as certain PEACE datasets might fall under the scope of the EU Regulation 2021/821 on dual-use export controls.

Lastly, as part of PEACE data management, we need to consider **other data handling procedures** stemming from the institutional practices of PEACE scientific members. These practices encompass the internal procedures of DLR, DTU, and BTU CS. Nevertheless, no explicit conflicts are anticipated, as all PEACE members are aligned with the open access policy². Each participating entity is responsible for complying with its own institutional data regulations, and in case of a potential conflict with the PEACE DMP, GG is to be informed and a conflict resolution procedure will be initiated.

² Broschüre (2018); DTU Library; University Library Cottbus-Senftenberg.

5. Conclusion

The PEACE Data Management Plan represents a living document that will guide the project consortium through the entire data lifecycle while adhering to the principles of the EU Open Science policy, including the FAIR principles of data management. The current document is a public version of project DMP which was delivered in M3 (August 2023) of the project implementation period when most of the scientific and technological tasks were yet to start, and some datasets information was still too early to be known. Nevertheless, it serves as a starting point for future updates in M18 and M36, which will present more mature versions of the PEACE data policy.

This version of the PEACE DMP covers digital research data generated within the project, along with other research outputs (namely public deliverables). It is based on information gathered from an internal survey conducted within the PEACE consortium during M1-M2 of the project implementation period.

The consortium has identified seven datasets and thirteen other research outputs that fall under the scope of this DMP. All datasets and outputs will be managed in accordance with the FAIR data principles, ensuring their findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. This approach aims to contribute to the successful realization of the PEACE objectives, thereby enriching the European realm of science and innovation.

6. References

4TU.Researchdata - <https://data.4tu.nl>

Broschüre: Grundlagen zum Forschungsdatenmanagement im DLR (2018), <https://www.dlr.de/de/medien/publikationen/broschueren/grundlagen-zum-forschungsdatenmanagement-im-dlr>

DTU Library – Open Access - <https://www.bibliotek.dtu.dk/en/publishing/open-access>,

EU Grants AGA - Annotated Grant Agreement, EU Funding Programmes 2021-2027, version 1.0, draft, April 2023 - https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

Grant Agreement, Project 101101343 – PEACE – HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2022-1

Open Energy Platform - <https://openenergy-platform.org/>

Regulation (EU) 2021/821 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 setting up a Union regime for the control of exports, brokering, technical assistance, transit and transfer of dual-use items

ScienceRepository - <https://sciencerepository.dk/>

University Library Cottbus-Senftenberg – Open Access - <https://www.b-tu.de/en/bibliothek/publishing/open-access#c136861>

ZENODO - <https://zenodo.org/>